

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

DEVELOPMENT OF IMMUNOGLOBULIN FOR TREATMENT OF COMPLICATED STAPHYLOCOCCAL INFECTION

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Abstract

The aim of the Project was to obtain safe, highly therapeutic anti-staphylococcal polyclonal purified immunoglobulin, which will help patients suffering from a severe form of staphylococcal infection to recover. The works and studies to develop immunoglobulin were including the following: selection of Staphylococci, obtaining and determining an activity of immunogens such as alpha-anatoxin, PV-leukocidin and hyaluronidase; Immunization of producer animals (goats) with immunogens; reception of hyper immune serum and extraction of immunoglobulin fraction; enzymatic processing of antibodies to obtain a harmless medicine (preparation); final product controls. 30 strains (*Staphylococcus aureus* -24, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* -6) having the stable characteristics were selected out of 102 strains collected from several Georgian Clinics, also one German and two strains from USA were used in these studies.

In order to obtain immune serum, the producer animals, have been vaccinated according to a pre-developed immunization schedule, with increasing doses of immunogens, with the addition of adjuvants. In the normal (K), immune serum and immunoglobulin the protective Antibody Titer was determined. For this purpose, hemolysis reaction (Lh), passive hemagglutination test (using dry diagnostic test systems) and immunoenzymatic analysis ("Sandwich-ELISA" method) were used. Antibody titer in immune preparations in hemolysis reaction to alpha-toxin was 150 IU/ml, in normal serum -0.5-1.0 IU/ml; The titer of Antibacterial Antibodies in the passive hemagglutination reaction was found to be as -1:6400 - 1:12800, of the anti-leukocidin antibodies - 1:640-1:1280, and for hyaluronidase - 1:160-1:320, the titer of the same antibodies in normal serum ranged from 1:10 to 1:40. These antibodies were determined by immunoenzymatic analyzes method. The average data of normal serum against alpha-toxin was 0.081; The index of positivity to the same toxin in immune serum amounted to 10.08; The index of positivity of antibacterial antibodies was equal to 9.2517. PV-leukocidin positivity index -4.3968, and hyaluronidase -0.9214. To remove anaphylactogenic Fc fragments from antibody molecules, we used enzyme (Pepsin) processing with a special kit "Pierce™ Fab Preparation Kit, USA".

The medicine (preparation) tested in accordance with the requirements of the European Pharmacopoeia was found to be sterile, non-toxic, reactogenic, stable and non-pyrogenic. Purified immunoglobulin's subcutaneous injection with the dose of 5 IU/ml -0.5 ml, protected 91.7% of white mice from an unconditionally lethal (Del) dose of pathogenic staphylococcus. Whereas mortality in control animals group was 100%.

Thus, a harmless medicine (preparation) of Antistaphylococcal purified Polyclonal Immunoglobulin, with high healing properties have been obtained.

Keywords: *S. aureus*, *S. epidermidis*, Staphylococcal infections, α -toxin, PV-leucocidin, hyaluronidaza, anti-staphylococcal immunoglobulin.

Introduction. Staphylococcus is a unique microorganism, it can cause more than 100 different diseases. Due to the increase of resistance to antibiotics, staphylococci as the main instigators of in-hospital and out-of-hospital infections have become an actual problem of modern medicine (Gerber J. et al. 2009; Liu C. et al, 2011; Backer KA, et al, 2017). The ability of staphylococci to damage any tissue and cell is due to a wide spectrum of pathogenic factors of the bacterium - enzymes and toxins. The latter, according to the mechanism of action, are divided into several groups: cell membrane-damaging exotoxins, exfoliative, toxic shock syndrome-causing toxins, enterotoxin - A, B, Ci2, D, E. Staphylococcus aureus can infect wounds and is a potential cause of osteomyelitis, endocarditis and bacteremia. In addition to the above, it can induce many serious nosocomial infections. *S. aureus* is often isolated from the body of patients suffering from hospital infections - especially from prosthetic and transplant patients (Mermel L.M, et al.2009; David M.Z, Daum R.S, 2017).

S. aureus causes a number of toxicoses, including toxic shock syndrome (TSS), food poisoning, toxic epidermal burns (cut skin syndrome), and necrotizing pneumonia.

Along with the creation of each new generation of antibiotics, the number of resistant strains increases significantly.

Penton-Valentine (PV) leukocidin synthesized by staphylococci causes the disintegration of neutrophils and other phagocytizing cells (Tromp A,T, et al, 2018), and hyaluronidase – damages the connective tissues of the body (Ibberson C.B, et al, 2016).

S. aureus virulence is also mediated by the adhesion factors CLFA and CLFB, which bind fibrinogen. Toxin A and B cause skin lesions and toxic epidermal necrolysis.

The lethality caused by *S. aureus* infections reaches 30%. Sepsis and mortality caused by *S. epidermidis* is higher (Falahee P.C, et al, 2017). Mortality caused by PV-leukocidin synthesizing strains reaches 80%.

Against the background of antibiotic resistance, specific bacteriophages are increasingly used for the treatment of bacterial infections, which, unlike antibiotics, do not have side effects. Since toxic factors are leading in the pathogenesis of complicated infection, the use of immune drugs with high activity is preferred. The unique property of antibodies is to neutralize the harmful effects of bacteria and toxins on cells and tissues. To date, for the treatment of staphylococcal infections, homologous (donor) antistaphylococcal immunoglobulin, which contains only antitoxic (alpha-toxin) antibodies (activity – 30 IU/ml). A homologous drug is generally useless for the treatment of infection caused by *S. epidermidis*. According to available data, this immunoglobulin is not characterized by high healing properties. At the same time it is expensive.

The purpose of the project: development of the technology of administration of antistaphylococcal polyclonal purified immunoglobulin and laboratory-experimental study.

Material and methods. Staphylococcal strains collected from different clinics and bacteriological centers of Georgia (Giorgi Eliava Institute of Bacteriophage, Microbiology and Virology; Academician V. Bochorishvili clinic; Kutaisi Hospital "MedicalCity"; Tbilisi Iashvili Children's Clinic; Kutaisi Microbiological Center - Mycobiologist LLC), as well as standard strains (USA-2, Germany-1) were studied.

The study of obtained virulent and conditionally pathogenic 102 clinical staphylococcal strains included morphological (shape, location, attitude to dyes, capsule production), cultural (growth on food areas, form of colonies), biochemical (NH₃ production, catalase activity, coagulation of citrated blood plasma, mannitol fermentation, hemolytic property) characteristics, susceptibility to novobiocin and staphylococcal bacteriophage to determine. The mentioned microbiological works were carried out by methods tested in laboratory practice, using growth characteristics, API differentiation tests on food areas; Antibiotic sensitivity of microbes was studied by disk diffusion method, and phage sensitivity with spot test assay by dropping commercial staphylococcal bacteriophage (phage purified by chromatography method, series P1-901,2019) on the lawn of microbes seeded on agar in Petri dishes.

In the experiments, we used standard liquid and solid nutrient media (Brain Heart Infusion Agar, Brain Heart Infusion Broth, Liofilchem, srl.ITALY).

To study the plasmocoagulation activity of the strains, we used Boczvari plasma (Coagulase plasma, Biolife, Milano, Italia, Exper date: 2021), while

Novobiocin (Liverpool L97, AR, Abtek Biological Ltd. Exper date:2021,07,UK) to determine antibiotic susceptibility.

Staphylococcal anatoxin was prepared in the laboratory of immunology with improved technology. Alpha-toxin (alpha-hemolysin) was obtained by inoculating Staphylococcus aureus 0-15 strain in casein soil with 5-day (twice a day) aeration with oxygen and carbon dioxide in certain proportions. The obtained native alpha-toxin was purified by stepwise precipitation at low temperature (0°C) first with 25% chemically pure sodium chloride, and in the next step by maintaining a certain ratio of trichloroacetic acid and medical alcohol (96°C). Refrigerated centrifuge (+2 -+3°C) was used to obtain insoluble alpha-hemolysin. We determined the activity of the purified alpha-toxin by the hemolysis reaction, using the erythrocytes of the bee. The activity of the received toxin amounted to 10 international units, which fully complies with the requirements of the technical documentation (Appendix 1, Appendix 2).

Diagnostic test systems (bacterial, alpha-toxin, PV-leukocidin, hyaluronidase) were prepared and lyophilized to evaluate the titer of anti-staphylococcal antibodies in blood serum using a standard method. The mentioned procedure was carried out by passive (indirect) hemagglutination reaction.

By cultivating the selected producer strain on Brain Heart Infusion soil, we obtained an active solution of leukocidin. The method of Sveicar J. and Vancurik J. (1959) was used to obtain PV-leukocidin. Staphylococcal culture was inoculated on sterile cellophane pre-coated with Br-Hrd agar in a Petri dish. We

placed the cups in a thermostat at 37°C for 12-18 hours. We washed the culture from one agar plate with 1 ml Hanks (or MEM) solution. We put the collected solution from petri dishes in a vial with beads and put it in the refrigerator for 3 hours. After the mentioned time, we kept the suspension in a +5 °C refrigerator for 20 minutes. In order to remove sticky impurities, the concentration of liquid hydrogen ions in the sediment containing leukocidin was adjusted to pH-5.0. The obtained clear solution was filtered through a sterilizing Millipore filter (0.22 µm). We corrected the concentration of hydrogen ions (pH=7.0 - 7.2) and determined the minimum leukocidin dose, which represents the maximum dilution of leukocidin, at which time only lymphocytes remain in the human blood added to the test tube, and neutrophils (granulocytes) undergo complete disintegration. The experiment showed that *Staphylococcus aureus* 015 was the most active producer among the tested pathogenic staphylococcal strains (Appendix 3).

Purified staphylococcal anatoxin and PV-leukocidin were prepared according to existing methods (Rigvava S. et al, 2020). In order to evaluate antibodies against immunogens, we have developed a diagnostic test system, which is used in the passive hemagglutination (Phar) reaction. To prepare a test system for loading formalinized erythrocytes (sensitization), we determined the optimal sensitization dose for a separate antigen. After the control check, the diagnostic reagent was dissolved in a protective solution (5.0% gelatose, 7.0% sucrose) and dried by the lyophilization method. We used commercial staphylococcal hyaluronidase in the experiments.

Goats were selected to receive immune serum. Our decision was based on the idea that they are easy to manage, administer vaccinations and draw blood. Based on many literary sources, it is known that goat blood serum proteins are 6-10 times less allergenic than horse blood serum. In order to obtain hyperimmune serum with high healing properties, we have developed a schedule for priming and hyperimmunization of producer animals (Appendix 4).

Within the framework of the project, to obtain the F(ab')₂ fragment from the anti-staphylococcal polyclonal immunoglobulin preparation, we used the special kit "Pierce™ Fab Preparation Kit, USA" produced by Thermo Scientific (USA) (2021) (Appendix 5), which contains the antibody F(ab')₂ all the components needed to obtain the fragment and is a fast and efficient means of receiving and purifying the mentioned product. The purification process included several stages: in the first, preparatory stage, we treated the immobilized enzyme (pepsin) column with specific buffers and centrifuged at 5000g for 1 minute; on second stage we prepared IgG, the content of which in the research sample should not exceed 4 mg/ml and in our case, it was 2 mg/ml. The third stage of the study was to cut the antibody with an enzyme and obtain the desired F(ab')₂ fragment, which is carried out by mixing the prepared samples together (IgG and immobilized pepsin), the mixture is incubated at 37°C for 0.5-2 hours, followed by centrifugation and washing with PBS buffer, and the final step was the chromatographic purification of the

resulting F(ab')₂ fragment, for what we ran the pepsin-treated preparation onto a NAb Protein A Plus Spin column equilibrated with PBS buffer. After mixing the sample with the sorbent for 10 minutes, we collected the fraction containing the purified F(ab')₂ fragments by centrifuging the chromatographic column for 1 minute at 1000 × g.

Some biochemical indicators of immunoglobulin were studied by us, namely, a) IgG concentration was determined by spectrophotometric method, b) stability of the drug, f) determination of the molecular weight of the drug. We analyzed the process of generation of F(ab')₂ fragments of pepsin-treated Ig preparation by gel-electrophoresis in polyacrylamide gel (SDS-PAGE).

We determined the level of antistaphylococcal antibodies in normal and immune goat serum, as well as in immunoglobulin, by immunoenzymatic method. The results were registered on an immunoenzymatic reader (Sunostik SPR-960). We used the following reagent for immunoenzymatic analysis: Anti-Goat IgG (H&L) in rabbit Affinity Purified, Polysciences, Inc.exp.10.2022. According to normal values 50-390 ng/ml immunoenzyme analysis has been performed based on common "Sandwich-ELISA" in accordance with the guidelines attached to the test-systems.

We controlled the toxicity in accordance with the requirements of the European Pharmacopoeia (EUROPEAN PHARMACOPOEIA, 5,0.2.6.9. Abnormal toxicity). For this purpose, we used animals: - non-linear white mice, live weight 18-22 g. - 5 pieces; - Guinea pigs- 2, live weight, respectively 260 and 300 g. Experiment: - test Ig was injected intraperitoneally into mice (0.5 ml) and guinea pigs (5.0 ml); We observed for 7 days and nights.

Control of sterility (EUROPEAN PHARMACOPOEIA, 2008. 2.6.1. Sterility) was performed on bacterial and fungal contamination. Immunoglobulin samples (series No. 1, 2, 3) were sown in Thioglycolate, Brain-Hert and Sabouraud media. We observed test tubes for sterility for 14 days and nights.

Control of harmlessness (reactogenicity): non-linear white mice (3) and guinea pigs (2) were injected subcutaneously in the ring area with 0.5 ml and 5 ml of test immunoglobulin (protein -1.72 mg/ml); We observed the animals for 7 days and nights (Appendix 6).

Control over stability. Experiment: 3 ampoules of purified transparent preparation (in each ampoule 1 ml of preparation, protein -Ic-1.71 mg/ml; IIc-1.72 mg/ml) were placed in a thermostat at 37 °C. Trial duration - 30 days.

Control of pyrogenicity. (EUROPEAN PHARMACOPOEIA 5.9. 01/2005. 2.6.8. PYROGENS, p.152) Control of pyrogenicity was carried out on 3 chinchillas of both sexes, whose live weight was 1.5-2.5 kg and body temperature - within 38.5°C - 39.5°C. Test immunoglobulin was injected intravenously at 37°C, 1 ml per 1 kg of live weight. We measured the body temperature of the animals three times with an interval of 1 hour.

Control over medicinal properties. The therapeutic properties were evaluated on the model of experimental staphylococcal infection, on non-linear white

mice, with a live weight of 18-22 g, intraperitoneally inoculated with a Dcl -dose of the pathogen (unconditionally lethal dose), according to the existing method. Immunoglobulin was injected 4 hours after the introduction of the pathogen. We observed the animals for 72 hours.

Control of prophylactic properties was carried out in the same way as therapeutic properties, but with the difference that initially we administered the test immunoglobulin in the same doses, four hours after administration of the drug, animals were immunized intraperitoneally with staphylococcal culture and alpha-toxin (Dcl).

Control for anaphylactogenicity. The purified preparation was tested in guinea pigs by the skin test (skin anaphylaxis)-over method. For this purpose, we used a 1% solution of Evans blue. In the sensitized guinea pigs, on the 21st day, the main dose of the test immunoglobulin, which is 5 times higher than the sensitization dose, was injected into the skin. After 5-7 minutes, 0.5 ml of Evans blue 1% solution was injected intracardially. In case of anaphylaxis, a dark blue spot develops 20 minutes after the administration of the decisive dose (Appendix 7).

We studied the control of inflammatory-necrotic properties, i.e., the Artius phenomenon, on the roaches (2 chinchillas). 4-fold subcutaneous injection of test immunoglobulin in a volume of 0.5 ml, with an interval of 6 days, leads to the slowing down of absorption and the development of an inflammatory reaction: hyperemia, edema, emigration of leukocytes. An intense inflammatory-necrotic reaction of the skin develops.

Results obtained and discussion

Conducting research work was carried out by working on bacteria using existing methods (EUCAST) and following standard laboratory practice procedures (SOP).

30 (*Staphylococcus aureus* - 24, *Staphylococcus epidermidis* -6) strains, including 2 from the American and one from the German collection, were selected from the 102 strains studied in the course of research.

Staphylococci cultures are characterized by similar morphological (Table 1) signs, namely cluster arrangement in smears, blue-violet staining (gram-positive), formation of S-shaped colonies on agar; However, there is an important difference that *S. aureus* is determined by the formation of a microcapsule, which *S. epidermidis* strains are lacking.

Table 1

Morphological characteristics of staphylococcal strains

#	Name the microbe	Number of strains	Gram staining	arrangement	Colony form	Production of microcapsules
1.	<i>S. aureus</i>	24	+	Bunch of grapes	S	+
2.	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	6	+	Bunch of grapes	S	-

A significant difference is noted in the studied strains in terms of enzyme activity (Table 2), which *S. aureus* was reflected in the lysis of erythrocytes, coagulation of citrated blood plasma, mannitol fermentation and proteolytic properties. The mentioned feature of *S. epidermidis* strains are not typical.

Table 2

Enzymatic characteristics of staphylococcal strains

#	Name the microbe	Number of strains	Plasmocogalatin	Mannitol fermentation	Hemolysis	Proteolysis
1.	<i>S. aureus</i>	24	+	+	+	+
2.	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	6	-	+	-	-

The study of the sensitivity of staphylococci to novobiocin and staphylococcal bacteriophage revealed the presence of resistant strains (Table 3). For example, *S. aureus* out of 24 strains, 19 were sensitive to novobiocin, 5 were resistant. *S. epidermidis* out of 6 strains

sensitive 4, resistant 2; against staphylophage *S. aureus* out of 24 strains, 13 were sensitive, 11 were non-sensitive, and *S. epidermidis* from 6 strains sensitive – 1, non-susceptible – 5.

Table 3

Antibiotic and phage sensitivity of staphylococcal strains

#	Name the microbe	Number of strains	Novobiocin		Staphylococcal bacteriophage	
			sensitive	Resistant	sensitive	Resistant
1.	<i>S. aureus</i>	24	19	5	13	11
2.	<i>S. epidermidis</i>	6	4	2	1	5

Complex studies included: the selection of producer animals (goats) according to the high titer of antitoxic antibodies obtained as a result of the initial inoculation of anatoxin (1.0 ml; 15 ml); preparing an effective combination of immunogens; hyperimmunization of producers with a developed schedule; receiving antistaphylococcal serum containing high-titer antibodies against immunogens. 3 weeks

after the initial vaccination, the producers were hyperimmunized with increasing doses of immunogens - heat-inactivated cultures of staphylococci, alpha-anatoxin, PV-leukocidin and hyaluronidase, subcutaneously. The immunization schedule is given in the table (No. 4).

Table 4

Immunization schedule of productive animals (goats)

№	Used immunogens	antigen dose/ml					taking blood		
		I injection	II injection	III injection	IV injection	V injection	sample on day VI	First collection on day VIII	Second collection on day X
1	Staphyloc. Anatoxin + 0.5% adjuvant – Kal(SO ₄) ₂	1	2	3,5	5				
2	Inactivated staphyloc. culture- 5 mlrd/ml, (85-96°C)+ Kal(SO ₄) ₂	0,5	1	2	4				
3	PV - Leukocidin + 0.5% Kal(SO ₄) ₂ mg,		0,1	0,2	0,4				
4	Hyaluronidase + 0.5% Kal(SO ₄) ₂ mg			0,2 mg	0,4				

In the hyperimmune serum produced in the laboratory of virology and immunology and the immunoglobulin obtained from it, we determined protective antibodies against pathogenic (*S. aureus*) and conditionally pathogenic (*S. epidermidis*) staphylococci and virulence factors, in particular, against the bacterial cell, alpha-toxin, PV-leukocidin and hyaluronidase. Standard diagnostic test-systems made for this purpose, which we used in the modern method of research - passive hemagglutination reaction (PHR).

The development of a staphylococcal diagnostic test system, which is used in medical and veterinary practice, is aimed at evaluating the post-vaccination immune response (determining the titer of antibodies), as well as diagnosing staphylococcal infection.

The passive (indirect) hemagglutination reaction, which is used in the republic only in the laboratory of virology and immunology of the Bacteriophage Institute, is widely used in cooking (3,4,5).

PHAR is a specific and highly sensitive method, easy to set up and gives a response in a short time - 1.5-2 hours (Appendix 8, Appendix 9).

One of the important stages in the preparation of a highly sensitive active test system is the stabilization of the adsorbent (erythrocytes)

Method selection. In practice, human erythrocytes of the first group and sheep (cow) and latex particles are mainly used. Different aldehydes are used to obtain standard erythrocytes. In our case, we used formaldehyde (15).

When preparing the test system, it should be taken into account that each milliliter of 2.5% suspension of formalinized erythrocytes should contain 500-600 thousand cells. In order to increase the sensitivity and specificity of the drug (to remove protein, polysaccharide and other impurities from the surface of the erythrocyte membrane), we treated the erythrocytes with potassium bichromate (K₂Cr₂O₇) at a dilution of 1:5000. We washed the erythrocytes with a 0.9% solution of sodium chloride and prepared a 2.5% suspension. In addition, in order to increase the sensitivity of the test system, we treated a 2.5% suspension of erythrocytes with tannic acid (5 ml of tannic acid is added to 5 ml of tan-

nin - concentration 2.0 x 10⁴) and placed in a thermostat at 37°C for 20 minutes, then we washed twice with 1/15 M phosphate buffer (pH=7.2) and once with 1/15 M phosphate buffer (pH=6.4).

Then, using the existing method, we performed erythrocyte sensitization (loading) with purified staphylococcal toxoid. The obtained results revealed that in terms of specific activity, the most sensitive is the test system, which is obtained by treating erythrocytes with a dilution of potassium bichromate at 1:5000.

In addition, in order to increase the sensitivity of the test system, we treated a 2.5% suspension of erythrocytes with tannic acid (we added 5 ml of tannic acid to 5 ml of tannin - concentration 2.0 x 10⁴) and placed it in a thermostat at 37°C for 20 minutes, then we washed it twice with 1/15 M phosphate buffer (pH=7.2) and once with 1/15 M phosphate buffer (pH=6.4). We diluted the washed erythrocytes with a 0.9% sodium chloride solution to a 2.5% suspension and added sensitin (antigen). As sensitin we used: purified staphylococcal bacterial antigen, alpha-anatoxin, PV-leukocidin and hyaluronidase. Thus, four different types of test-systems, 3-3 microseries each, were produced.

The preparation of a highly sensitive drug is conditioned by the determination of the optimal dose of sensitin, which is the basis for the serial production of the test system. The optimal dose of sensitin (anatoxin) is the experimentally established amount of anatoxin, which reveals antitoxic antibodies in the maximum dilution, and gives us a strongly negative reaction in control tests. It can be seen from the table (No. 5) that the anatoxin dose of 30 µg/ml for 5 ml of 2.5% suspension of erythrocytes is very small (titer 11.42±2.37). In the case of a high dose of anatoxin - 140 - 150 µg/ml, it will reveal a high titer, although controls tend to be positive, creating a risk of overdiagnosis. The most optimal is the amount of anatoxin 80 µg/ml, which gives a high antibody titer, the controls are satisfactory. We used the mentioned dose to make microseries of the test system. Using the optimal dosage, we prepared 3 lyophilized microseries of the Anatoxin diagnostic test system, each with the amount of 35-40 ampoules (Appendix 10).

Optimal diagnostic of staphylococcal anatoxin dose determination

#	Number of formalized erythrocytes	Ana-toxin dose	Antibody titer range	accepted Result in PHR(M±m) *	Probability of differences (P)
1.	5.5×10^5	30	5–20	11.42±2.37	
2.	5.5×10^5	80	16–640	457.1±88.7	<0.01
3.	5.5×10^5	150	160–640	434.3±97.2	

Note * - horse's blood is used in passive hemagglutination reaction Staphylococcal antitoxic immunoglobulin (100 ME/ml).

In addition to anatoxin (80 µg/ml), the optimal dose for bacterial antigen was determined to be 140-150 µg/ml; for PV-leukocidin - 60-70 µg/ml, and for hyaluronidase - 45-50 µg/ml. The mentioned doses were the basis for the production of microseries of test systems. We dissolved the received diagnostic preparations in a protective medium (5% gelatose, 7% sucrose, 100 ml of sterile physiological solution), froze them at minus 40 °C and dried them in a lyophilic sublimation device. Diagnostic test systems are used in passive (indirect) hemagglutination reaction. The mentioned test in its specificity and sensitivity is equal to the immunoenzymatic analysis and is used in scientific and practical activities in the world.

Anatoxin diagnostic test system, in addition to the above, can be used for expert control of anti-staphylococcal immunoglobulin to detect adulterated drug.

The conducted complex studies included: the selection of producer animals (goats) according to the high titer of antitoxic antibodies obtained as a result of the initial inoculation of anatoxin (1.0 ml; 1.5 ml); preparing an effective combination of immunogens; hyperimmunization of producers with a developed schedule; Receiving antistaphylococcal serum containing high-titer antibodies against immunogens, separating the immunoglobulin fraction and receiving the F(ab')₂-fraction purified by the acid-enzymatic method and conducting controls on safety, medicinal properties, etc.

To receive immune serum, it is important to choose the correct immunization scheme and observe the intervals between injections of immunogens. The immunization cycle consisted of 4-5 injections. Immunogens were injected subcutaneously in increasing doses, with an interval of 6-7 days.

In the first stage, animals were primed with staphylococcal toxoid; Based on the evaluation of antitoxic antibodies in blood serum (not less than 10 IU/ml), producer animals were selected, which after 3 weeks were hyperimmunized according to the developed schedule with increasing doses of thermo-inactivated staphylococci cultures, alpha-anatoxin, PV-leukocidin and hyaluronidase, subcutaneously. The immunization scheme is given in the table (#4).

On the 8th and 10th day after the fourth injection, blood was taken from the producer animals (250-300 ml from each) after the control check.

In accordance with the existing technology, using the alcoholic fractionation method (Cohn E.G. et al, 1951), we obtained immunoglobulin in which the amount of protein was 10.3% (2.1 mg/ml).

Antibodies in normal, immune serum and immunoglobulin were examined by serological tests. We determined the antibody titer against α-toxin in the Lh (limes-haemolysis) reaction, which was 150 IU/ml; The range of antibacterial antibody titer in immune serum and immunoglobulin in passive hemagglutination test - 1:3200 – 1:12800; The titer of anti-leukocidin antibodies was 1:640 – 1:1280, and against hyaluronidase – 1:320 – 1:640. The mentioned indicators in normal serum ranged from 1:10-1:40.

Antistaphylococcal antibodies in normal goat serum, as well as in antistaphylococcal immunoglobulin solution were determined by the immunoenzyme method, the results of which were recorded on an immunoenzymatic reader (Sunostik SPR-960). We used the reagent: Anti-Goat IgG (H&L) in rabbit Affinity Purified, Polysciences, Inc. exp. 10.2022 to conduct the mentioned test. According to normal values 50-390 ng/ml immunoenzyme analysis has been performed based on common "Sandwich-ELISA" in accordance with the guidelines attached to the test-systems.

The average data of normal (control) sera for staphylococcal toxin was 0.081; And the positivity index of immune serum and immunoglobulin in relation to the mentioned toxin - 10.08. Antibacterial antibody positivity index was 9.2517, PV-leukocidin positivity index was -4.3968, and hyaluronidase -0.9214.

The concentration of IgG in the study immunoglobulin (native, C2) preparations was calculated by GENESIS 100UV Scanning spectrophotometer using the absorbance at 280 nm, IgG extinction coefficient (210,000 M⁻¹ cm⁻¹) and molecular weight (150,000 g/mol). As a control, we took standard Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA-Sigma), Table 6.

Table 6

IgG concentration in antistaphylococcal immunoglobulin preparations

#	Medicine	dilution	optical density (OD) 280 nm	concentration of immunoglobulins in the drug, mg/ml
1	IgG (solution), ampoule	1/12	0.246	2.11
2	IgG (solution), ampoule	1/24	0.118	2.02
3	IgG (powder), 1% suspension	1/10	0.141	1.01
4	Control: BSA (Sigma) powder, 1 mg/ml	-	0.673	BSA concentration in the sample= 1.02 mg/ml

According to the received data, the concentration of IgG in the native, undiluted drug is 2.11 mg/ml. In addition to the above, we performed an analysis of the protein structure of immunoglobulin in polyacrylamide gel-electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE), which revealed the difference in concentration in the preparations.

At the same time, we determined some indicators of non-specific immunity in producers: namely, phagocytic index, digestibility, complement C3 and C4 components. E.g. In the blood serum of producer No. 9, an increase in complement indicators was found to be statistically reliable. C3 and C4 - data were 88.7 mg/dL and 15.1 mg/dL, respectively, and similar indicators in immune serum were 183.8 mg/dL and 45.0 mg/dL.

Thus, as a result of the conducted studies, pathogenic (*S. aureus*) and conditionally pathogenic (*S. epidermidis*) strains of staphylococci with stable characteristics were selected; a staphylococcal alpha-anatoxin, PV-leukocidin, has been produced and tested. By immunization of producer animals with staphylococcal immunogens, anti-staphylococcal polyclonal immune serum is obtained, the corresponding immunoglobulin is isolated by the method of alcohol fractionation. Serological examination showed that they contain antibacterial, antitoxic (alpha-toxin, PV-leukocidin) and anti-enzymatic (hyaluronidase) antibodies in high titers. In total, 3 microseries of native immunoglobulin were produced: Series No. 1 - 153 ampoules; No. 2 series - 200 ampoules; No. 3 series - 180 ampoules. Each

ampoule contains 2 ml of the drug; Protein content - 10.2-10.3%, i.e. 2.1 mg/ml.

One of the main goals of the project was to remove or drastically reduce possible allergic properties of polyclonal immunoglobulin using a high-tech method, which is possible by removing the allergy-inducing Fc-fragment from the antibody molecule using enzyme-pepsin. To obtain the purified protective F(ab')₂ fragment of the antibody, we used a special kit provided by Thermo Scientific (USA) "Pierce™ Fab Preparation Kit, USA" (Catalog #:PI44988), which contains F(ab')₂. All the components needed to get the fragment. Cleaning includes several stages: in the first, preparatory stage, we treated the immobilized pepsin column included in the kit with specific buffer solutions. The next stage was the preparation of the test sample of IgG. The sample (5 mg/ml) was collected in special column centrifuge tubes. The next stage is the separation of F(ab')₂ fragment and Fc-fragment of the antibody. For this purpose, we added immobilized pepsin to the prepared IgG samples and fractionated them using a chromatographic column. The last step involved the purification of the obtained F(ab')₂ fragment. The obtained results were evaluated spectrophotometrically and by protein electrophoresis in polyacrylamide gel (SDS-PAGE). A reliable result was obtained by the effect of pepsin on the antibody at -pH-3.5 and under the conditions of exposure to 37°C for 2 hours (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Generation and purification of antistaphylococcal immunoglobulin F(ab')₂ fragment. Protein electrophoresis in polyacrylamide gel (SDS-PAGE).

1. IgG initial preparation;
2. IgG preparation Zeba desalting by running on a chromatographic column in a modified buffer (pH 3.5);
3. Marker (PageRuler Broad Range Protein Ladder);
4. IgG preparation after treatment with pepsin (pH 3.5, 24 h);
- 5, 6 and 7. F(ab')₂ fragment obtained by chromatographic purification of the pepsin-treated NAB Protein A plus Spin column.

For in vitro and in vivo purified immunoglobulin controls, 43 ampoules from each of the three series were used. We have stored under proper conditions: I - series - 5 ampoules (1 ml in each); II - series - 10 ampoules; III - series - 10 ampoules (Appendix 11).

We controlled the toxicity in animals: - non-linear white mice, live weight 18-22 g. - 5 pieces; - Guinea pigs, live weight, 260 g and 300 g. - 2 pieces. Experiment: - we injected experimental Ig intraperitoneally to mice (0.5 ml) and guinea pigs (5.0 ml); we observed for 7 days and nights. All animals remained alive, which confirms that the trial immunoglobulin is non-toxic.

Sterility was controlled for bacterial and fungal contamination. For this purpose, immunoglobulin samples (series no. 1, 2, 3) were sown in Thioglycolate,

Brain-Hert and Sabouraud media. We observed test tubes for sterility for 14 days and nights. During the observation period (14 days), there was no growth of bacteria and fungi.

Controls for safety (reactogenicity) were performed in non-linear white mice (3) and guinea pigs (2). 0.5 ml and 5 ml of test immunoglobulin (protein - 1.72 mg/ml) were injected into the ring area under the skin of the animals; No clinical signs of disease were observed in the animals during the observation period (7 days). Thus, the purified immunoglobulin is harmless, i.e. reactogenic (Appendix).

Control over stability. In the experiment, we took 3 ampoules of purified transparent preparation (1 ml of preparation in each ampoule, protein - I s-1.71 mg/ml; II s-1.72 mg/ml), placed in a thermostat at 37°C. Trial duration - 30 days. Immunoglobulin remained clear, no so-called "gelation" and flocculation. The reading of the optical density on the spectrophotometer was practically unchanged, which was confirmed by gel electrophoresis of the proteins in the polyacrylamide gel (SDS-PAGE, Figure 2).

Figure 2. Control of immunoglobulin (IgG) thermostability by gel electrophoresis in polyacrylamide gel (SDS-PAGE, concentrating gel - 3%, separating gel - 7%).

Samples: IgG (+4°C) (100 X gz.); IgG (+37°C) (100 X gln.); BSA (0.2mg/ml).

Therefore, the test immunoglobulin does not change its properties under the influence of temperature and remains stable (Table 7)

Table 7

Antistaphylococcal immunoglobulin (IgG, C2) preparation optical control of thermo stability

wave length (nm)	Drug N 1 (+4 °C)	Drug N 2 (+37°C)	The difference between 37° C and 4o C between the optical densities of drugs (Δ OD)
	optical density (OD)		
400	1.512	1.547	0.035
540	0.161	0.183	0.0220*

• - Similar results were obtained for other immunoglobulins (hour1, hour 3).

Control of pyrogenicity was carried out on 3 chinchillas of both sexes, whose live weight was 1.5-2.5 kg and body temperature - within 38.5°C - 39.5°C. Test immunoglobulin warmed (37°C) was injected intravenously, 1 ml per 1 kg of live weight. We measured the body temperature of the animals three times with an interval of 1 hour. The tests showed that the total temperature fluctuation of all three bottles did not exceed 1.4 °C, which is acceptable and confirms the apyrogenicity of the test immunoglobulin.

Therapeutic properties were evaluated on the model of experimental staphylococcal infection, on non-linear white mice, with a live weight of 18-22 g, injected intraperitoneally with the Dcl-dose of the pathogen (unconditionally lethal dose), according to the existing method. In the second group (5 IU/ml of the drug), 1 mouse died -8.3%, 11 survived (91.7%). Which proves that antistaphylococcal test immunoglobulin is characterized by high healing properties.

Control of prophylactic properties was carried out in the same way as curative properties, but with the difference that at first the test immunoglobulin was administered intravenously in the same doses, four hours after the administration of the drug, the animals

(6 mice) were immunized intraperitoneally with staphylococcal culture and alpha-toxin (Dcl). In the second and third groups, all 12 white mice survived (100.0%). Animals of the control group were killed within 20-25 hours. The result showed that anti-staphylococcal polyclonal trial immunoglobulin has high prophylactic properties.

Control of anaphylactogenicity - The purified preparation was tested in guinea pigs by the skin test (skin anaphylaxis) -over method. For this purpose, we used a 1% solution of Evans blue, and 20 minutes after administration of the drug, 0.5 ml of 1% Evans was intracardially injected into the sensitized animals. No blue spot was noted in the animals of the experimental group, only one showed a slight skin change. Over's method revealed that the purified drug is not characterized by an anaphylactogenic reaction.

We studied the control of inflammatory-necrotic properties, i.e., the Artius phenomenon, on the roaches (2 Rabbit). Test immunoglobulin was injected subcutaneously 4 times, with an interval of 6 days. Result: the drug does not cause the development of inflammatory-necrotic process.

Conclusions:

1. A completely new drug has been received - anti-staphylococcal polyclonal purified immunoglobulin, the purpose of which is to treat complicated staphylococcal (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus epidermidis*) infection.

2. The improved technology of receiving immunoglobulin has been developed, which ensures the receiving of high-quality purified β - and γ - globulin fractions without loss.

3. Polyclonal immunoglobulins are initially highly active and specific (IgG) antibodies: against pathogenic and conditionally pathogenic staphylococcal bacteria, alpha-toxin (alpha-hemolysin), PV-leukocidin and hyaluronidase.

4. We examined antibodies in normal, immune serum and immunoglobulin serologically. We determined the antibody titer against α -toxin in the Lh (limes-haemolysis) reaction, which was 140-160 IU/ml; The range of antibacterial antibody titer in immune serum and immunoglobulin in passive hemagglutination test -1:3200 – 1:12800; The titer of anti-leukocidin antibodies was 1:640 – 1:1280, and against hyaluronidase – 1:160 – 1:320. The mentioned indicators in normal serum ranged from 1:10-1:40.

The average data of normal (control) sera in the immunoenzymatic analysis against staphylococcal toxin amounted to 0.081; and the index of positivity of immune serum and immunoglobulin in relation to the mentioned toxin - 10.08; Antibacterial antibody positivity index 9.2517, PV-leukocidin positivity index -4.3968, and hyaluronidase -0.9214.

5. The new immunoglobulin is characterized by harmlessness. We use a special kit to obtain purified (harmless) F(ab')₂ fragments „Pierce™ Fab Preparation Kit, USA”.

6. Antistaphylococcal polyclonal immunoglobulin is characterized by high healing properties. 5 IU/ml of the drug) protects 91.7% of white mice from an unconditionally (Dcl) lethal dose of virulent staphylococci (5 billion/ml). The same dose kills control animals in 20-24 hours.

7. It was established experimentally: the drug is sterile, non-toxic, harmless (reactogenic), non-pyrogenic, stable, not characterized by anaphylactogenicity, does not cause the development of inflammatory-necrotic processes (Artius phenomenon).

8. Purified staphylococcal α -toxin (alpha-hemolysin) was obtained with improved technology. As a result of 10-day treatment with formaldehyde, staphylococcal toxoid (200 ampoules) was obtained, which we used as an immunogen for immunizing producers and sensitin for the preparation of a diagnostic test system.

9. An anatoxin diagnostic test system has been developed to determine the titer of staphylococcal antitoxic antibodies in the blood serum of people and animals. The test system can be used in the passive (indirect) hemagglutination reaction to diagnose staphylococcal infection in patients.

10. A PV-leukocidin diagnostic test system has been developed for the detection of anti-leukocidin

antibodies in human and animal blood serum. The test system can be used for diagnostics in the clinic and in scientific activities.

11. A hyaluronidase diagnostic test system has been developed to detect antibodies against hyaluronidase in human and animal blood serum. The test system can be used to diagnose staphylococcal infection.

12. "A positive decision has been issued on the basis of the formula of the invention" by LSI "Sakpatent" (letter No. 3124.1, 2023-06-01).

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